

Off-axis spanning detector for the Hyper-Kamiokande long- baseline oscillation program

中間検出器

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The Hyper-Kamiokande long-baseline (LBL) neutrino oscillation program

- Aim to make a conclusive measurement of δ_{CP} by precisely studying oscillations of $\nu_\mu \rightarrow \nu_e$ and $\bar{\nu}_\mu \rightarrow \bar{\nu}_e$ with J-PARC beam neutrinos

Beam neutrinos

ν_e candidates @ FD

Basically same setup as T2K

Baseline	295km
Off-axis angle	2.5 degree
Flux peak energy	0.6 GeV
Matter effect	Marginally small

- The combination of **187 kton** of FD's fiducial mass and **1.3 MW** J-PARC beam yields ~ 20 times higher event rates than T2K
- After 10 years, **>1000 signal events can be collected** for each beam mode, providing an unprecedented sensitivity to δ_{CP}

Sensitivities to CP violation

Effects of systematic uncertainties

- 5 σ in first 3 years for $\delta_{CP} \sim -90^\circ$
- After 10 years
 - 5 σ CPV for 60% of the parameter space
 - 1 σ error uncertainty: 20 $^\circ$ for $\delta_{CP} \sim -90^\circ$, 6 $^\circ$ for $\delta_{CP} \sim 0$
- Controlling $\nu_e/\bar{\nu}_e$ cross-section systematic uncertainties is the key to success
 - Aim to reduce $\sim 5\%$ to $\sim 3\%$

Challenges to $\nu_e/\bar{\nu}_e$ measurements at NDs

- The FD observes ν_e flux oscillating from ν_μ with the peak energy of 0.6GeV \rightarrow **CCQE** dominant
- To measure **CCQE**, the NDs are forced to utilize intrinsic ν_e flux that:
 - has higher energy than the FD \rightarrow **the non-QE irreducible background events** [explain later]
 - exists as $\sim 1\%$ fraction of the neutrino beam \rightarrow excellent particle identification (PID)

Near detectors

ND280

IWCD
(Intermediate Water Cherenkov Detector)

Electron neutrino candidates @ Hyper-K

(10 years, 2.7×10^{22} POT, $\nu : \bar{\nu} = 1 : 3$)

	Total	$\nu_{\mu} \rightarrow \nu_e$	$\bar{\nu}_{\mu} \rightarrow \bar{\nu}_e$	Beam $\nu_e / \bar{\nu}_e$	Neutral current
ν -mode beam	2785 evts	81%	<1%	12%	6%
$\bar{\nu}$ -mode beam	1543 evts	15%	51%	24%	10%

● (●) : Primarily constrained by ND280 (IWCD)

- Will control beam flux & interaction cross-section uncertainties by a combination of ND280 & IWCD

IWCD facility

- New near detector facility to be constructed outside the J-PARC area
- The civil construction started in March 2025
- Completion of the pit excavation scheduled in 2027

Ground-breaking ceremony

Aug. 2025

Off-axis spanning detector - IWCD

- 600 tonnes-scale water Cherenkov detector
 - Observe neutrinos with **the same detection principle** as the FD
- The two novelties enables **$\nu_e/\bar{\nu}_e$ measurements** with the required precision of $\sim 3\%$
 - **mPMT modules**
 - **Moving capability by floatation system**

Floatation system

PID with mPMTs

- mPMT: 19 8-cm PTMs placed in waterproof vessel at an angle
- The **high granularity** and **directionality** allow detecting detailed pattern of Cherenkov lights, providing excellent PID performance

ν_e candidates @ IWCD (10 years, ν -mode)

Mis-PID
 $\nu_\mu/\bar{\nu}_\mu, \gamma$

Constraining non-QE with moving capability

ν_e candidates @ FD

ν_e candidates @ IWCD

non-QE
background
events

Reconstructed E_ν (GeV)

- IWCD has non-negligible **non-QE background** in the region of interest for CPV
- **Non-QE** cannot get constrained by single energy flux as its event topology is the same as CCQE (analogy: two unknowns in one equation)
- Thanks to moving capability, IWCD can collect neutrino data with **different energy fluxes**, enabling a **statistical separation** of CCQE and non-QE

$\times 10^{13}$ Beam fluxes (A.U.)

non-QE
enriched

Detector components

- Various detector components (mPMTs, calibration devices, water purification system, DAQ) have been prototyped and tested in the WCTE experiment at CERN
- Design finalization is being made, and full production will start in 2026

WCTE detector

(40 tonnes fixed water Cherenkov detector)

Detector tank

- Photosensor assembly procedures have studied with a mock-up at J-PARC
- The engineering design work for entire detector system (tank, supporting structure, moving system, etc) is ongoing
 - Planning onsite construction work for Autumn 2027

Overall schedule

- Aim to start collecting beam data with both Hyper-K and IWCD in May 2028

Summary

- The Hyper-Kamiokande long-baseline neutrino oscillation program aims to make a **conclusive measurement of δ_{CP}** including a discovery of CPV
- To achieve this, **IWCD** will be built to control **$\nu_e/\bar{\nu}_e$ cross-section uncertainty**
- Status of IWCD
 - Facility: civil construction has started in 2025
 - Detector components: both prototyping and testing have been performed
 - Detector tank: engineering design work is ongoing
- Plans of IWCD
 - **Autumn 2027**: completion of pit excavation followed by detector construction work
 - **Spring 2028**: start of beam neutrino observation together with Hyper-K FD

Intermediate Water Cherenkov Detector

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